

INTERRELATIONSHIP OF THE SCIENCE "HISTORY OF PEDAGOGY" IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF HUMAN SOCIETY.

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Annotasiya: In this article, the history of the development of the science of pedagogy, its problems and the theories of scientists in the history of the development of the science, as well as scientific views and opinions are highlighted.

Key words: Avesta, pedagogical views, education, traditions, values, folk pedagogy.

The glory of our independence is that the distortion of history has been stopped. It was proved by our scientists that the educational and cultural views of the peoples who lived on the land of Turan were high from the earliest times. It is known that the peoples of Central Asia, with a long and rich history, have created and improved their huge educational heritage and taught hundreds of generations of humanity universal human values such as humanity, science, kindness, hard work, friendship, and generosity. The educational ideas created by our people, brought up in the spirit of virtues, go back to ancient times. Historically, the Uzbek people have created their own special gift in the field of education. Even in the period when Zoroastrian religion was widespread in the land where the Uzbek people live today, pedagogical ideology ruled. This is expressed in some pages of the holy book of Zoroastrian religion "Avesta" that has reached us.

However, the possibility of covering the history of education, science and culture of the pre-Islamic period is limited. Because, at first, the Greek-Macedonian troops led by Alexander, and then the Arab conquerors led by Qutayba ibn Muslim, caused almost all the works and sources of that period to be lost. But the scientific study, careful analysis and application of existing pedagogical views of Islam and post-Islam, national educational traditions, values, folk pedagogy is an important and urgent problem of today. Until we achieved independence, we used and studied European pedagogy as a basis for our educational work. The task now is to focus on studying the most advanced

traditions of Eastern pedagogy and Western pedagogy. Because science first developed in the East.

The great German scientist Herler was right when he said: "The East is the teacher of Europe." The above thoughts alone can be the basis for saying that culture and enlightenment spread from the East to Europe. Because the emergence of schools of literacy and ancient writings in the oldest sources, "Avesta", Sogd, Bactrian, Urhun-Yenisei, Khorezm and other writings were written in the land of Turan, and the oldest ancestors of the peoples living in this holy land are literate people. . Indeed, the cultural heritage of the Uzbek people is a vast sea. There are so many great events that have been forgotten in our past that it is our first task to study them carefully and comprehensively.

The methodology of the history of pedagogy is based on national and universal values, folk pedagogy, the scientific and spiritual heritage of Central Asian and Eastern thinkers, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the speeches of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev on education and national independence. theories about motherhood.

It is known that in the past, people satisfied their needs in the process of working, and this process helped the young generation to acquire skills and qualifications. In the most ancient times, we can see valuable information about education in the examples of folklore, legends, heroic epics, songs, proverbs and sayings.

Because in folk oral art, which is a mirror of folk wisdom, educational experiences characteristic of folk pedagogy are generalized. Especially, the legend of the lamp mentioned in Poliene's "Military Tricks" and the legends about brave Thomaris in Herodotus' book "History" are among them. In the work "Devonu Lugotit Turk" by M. Kashgari, the image of learning, respecting educated and wise people, promoting hospitality, good manners, bravery, and self-interested, greedy, miserly, greedy, there are many poems that criticize negative aspects such as betrayal of friends and people. Such poems show that the Turkic people have paid great attention to education in the formation of human personality since ancient times.

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